

IR00000014 - ITSERR

ITSERR DMP

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00.01	01/12/2023	DRAFT	Initial Draft	
00.02	04/01/2024	DRAFT	Draft	First revision and addition of DM material proposed to research teams
01.00	27/09/2024	FINAL	Final	Verified by CNR

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	5
2	Initial DMP	6
2.1	ADMIN DETAILS	6
2.2	DATA SUMMARY	6
2.3	FAIR	7
2.3.1	MAKING DATA FINDABLE	7
2.3.2	MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE	9
2.3.3	MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	10
2.3.4	MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	12
2.4	COSTS AND ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	13
2.5	DATA STORAGE AND SECURITY	13
2.6	ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS	14
3	DMP material created for the ITSERR project.....	15
4	DMP webinars and training	15

List of Figures

Figure 1: IOSSG Template for ITSERR as implement on openaire.eu platform11
Figure 2: Metadata dataset of the Software DMP propose to Argos/OpenAIRE 12

List of Tables

No table of figures entries found.

1 Introduction

This document contains the data management plan (DMP) for ITSERR, which sets out the parameters for archiving, accessing and disseminating the data generated by the project. The DMP defines the guidelines for dealing with the types of data produced and is kept up to date during the project, making it an effective means of work for those activities of the project that collect, create or disseminate data.

This document contains the Initial DMP.

This plan is based on:

Data management plan template for Horizon 2020

2 Initial DMP

2.1 ADMIN DETAILS

Project Name: ITSERR - ITSERR DMP

Project Identifier: Iro000014

Project Data Contact: Michele CARRAGLIA; michele.carraglia@cnr.it

Description:

ITSERR is based on the postulate that the Humanities can offer superdiverse datasets whose complexity challenges technologies and ICT scholars. Therefore, the project aims at transforming the scientific community of Religious Studies from being a mere actor in the implementation of established technologies to the driver of a new match with the new assets of Artificial Intelligence/Big Data/HPC.

The project is implemented to:

- strengthen the RESILIENCE RI in its preparatory phase, through its national institutional dimension, scientific positioning, technical development and public perception.
- support excellence by putting the more qualified scholars and researchers in Religious Studies and ICT at the service of the excellence in research in Religious Studies, producing disruptive innovation for the domain.
- advance efficiency with the improvement of the accessibility to data, facilities and experts belonging to the national context and promoting data FAIRness;
- expand the RI national network of researchers, users and stakeholders, and be able to translate the national experience on other national contexts and at the European level.
- enhance operativity by offering new services and tools that are ready to be accessed by the end of the project and can thus rapidly enable new research scenarios and
- attract scholarship, research and industry to leverage the Italian scientific community of Religious Studies towards a more innovation-oriented research methodology.

2.2 DATA SUMMARY

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The data collected or generated as part of ITSERR is intended to support and document the activities necessary for all 8 research work packages and support the building the RESILIENCE research infrastructure (RI) in the field of Religious Studies.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The project generates textual and numeric data, mainly in MS Office formats. The use of open formats, such as .csv, etc. is encouraged. The data is used for analytics but also for Artificial Intelligence Machine Learning. In such case, the data is usually unstructured in .txt formats.

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

The project uses religious studies and linguistic data generated during the planning and building of other RI's that is openly accessible. The project collects data from the field of Religious Studies to gain an overview of the field of Religious Studies (e.g. experts, datasets descriptions...). Similar data from the previous phase of ITSERR will also be re-used. In some rare cases, license data has been ordered to support the research.

What is the origin/source of the data?

Most data results from previous research activities in Religious Studies. This is data coming from dissemination and communication, networking, coordination, support services, surveys and dialogues with stakeholders, learning exercises etc. This type of data relates to scientific publications so in the strict sense and does concern research data. Computer source code resulting from the development activities by AI and IT development teams, who contribute to the development of a new generation of religious studies tooling. To be noted that WP 9 – Taurus is generating 3D Scanning images of cuneiform tablets.

What is the expected size of the data?

The storage needed for the data created and gathered for the execution and management of this project and all its work packages will be limited in size since it will mainly concern text, .csv, pdf, etc. Files. However, it is to be noted that some WP like WP 9 – Taurus is generating 3D Scanning images of cuneiform tablets that uses up quite some amount of data and some other like WP7 is using raw scanned image for Optical Character recognition (OCR) and Hand-written Text recognition (HTR). and some image material. Some audio and video recordings of trainings, online meetings and workshops will be stored as well.

We estimate a max. size of 20 TB.

To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?

Public data can be useful for other projects related to disciplines such as all religious studies disciplines also including many other humanities disciplines such as linguistic, archaeology, history, etc. And also, Information Technology such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Artificial Intelligence. The data will also be useful to the RESILIENCE RI in its aim to design, plan and build a RI.

2.3 FAIR

2.3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?

ITSERR does create research data related to scientific research publications. In a majority of cases relevant and possible (e.g. in case there are no IPR or privacy issues) data and documents produced in the

framework of ITSERR will be made findable and accessible via Zenodo and be assigned pertinent and consistent metadata. Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments. Specific actions and their results, as well as other outputs, were also disseminated and made accessible via the dedicated project website. Documents for internal use will not require metadata because they are intended for people involved in the project. For this, naming conventions for files and folders should suffice.

How will you identify the datasets? Will you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as DOIs or handles?

Data and documents created by the ITSERR consortium as part of daily activities of the RI are stored and managed using Google Drive services. This data is to be only findable to the consortium. For all research data and documents, we will publish them with a public status findable and accessible via Zenodo where a DOI is issued to every published record.

How will you handle naming conventions for files and folders?

Documents will be named following this naming convention:

ITSERR_[WP number]_[Title]_[VersionID]_[Draft/Final status].

For deliverables, the number of the deliverable precedes the title:

ITSERR_[WP number]_[Deliverable number]_[Title]_[VersionID]_[Draft/Final status]

The minutes of meetings include 'MM' after 'ITSERR'.

In repositories used by the consortium, folders are structured according to work units. For the storage of data and working documents, the folders are structured according to task. This will help those working for the consortium find what they need.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Data and documents with a public status accessible via Zenodo will be provided with search keywords. Documents for internal use will not be assigned keywords because it is intended for people involved in the project. For this, naming conventions for files and folders should suffice.

Detail how you will deal with versioning. Will you provide clear version numbers if several versions of the data are kept?

Versions of documents, both deliverables and other documents, both public and confidential, should be inserted in the table Change History in the ITSERR word template.

1. The first version of the document is always: ID: 00.01 / Name: First draft / Status: DRAFT

2. For every major revision, ID and Name change accordingly, but the Status doesn't: ID: 00.02; 00.03; 00.04; ... / Name: Working Version; First revisioned text; EB revised version; ... / Status: DRAFT
3. The Final draft version is named as follows: ID: 01.00 / Name: Final Version / Status: FINAL

2.3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

ITSERR will create research data such as:

- Research papers
- Datasets for Machine Learning
- Datasets for Research
- Training material
- Software and source code
- Various documentation

In these cases, when relevant and possible (e.g. there are no IPR or privacy issues) the consortium will make data and documents related to the design of the RI with a public status findable and accessible. Personal data from survey results (ie for WP6 collecting information on attacks on religious places) or workshops that cannot be anonymized will not be made openly available and will be protected in accordance to GDPR.

How will the data that you will share be made accessible?

First, each Work Package must produce its DMP using describing its data and software management plan. This will be performed on the <https://argos.openaire.eu> platform.

For the following data types:

- Research papers: mandatorily on Zenodo and other research publication platforms
- Datasets for Machine Learning: mandatorily on Zenodo if not limited by size, also on HuggingFace.co platform (<https://huggingface.co/itserr>) and on the ITSERR platform (<https://www.itserr.it/>)
- Datasets for Research: mandatorily on Zenodo if not limited by size, also on GitHub platform (<https://github.com/itserr-resilience>) and on the ITSERR platform (<https://www.itserr.it/>)
- Training material: mandatorily on Zenodo if not limited by size, also on YouTube ITSERR channel and on the ITSERR platform (<https://www.itserr.it/>)
- Software and source code: mandatorily on Zenodo if not limited by size, also on gitHub platform (<https://github.com/itserr-resilience>) and on the ITSERR platform (<https://www.itserr.it/>)
- Various documentation: mandatorily on Zenodo if not limited by size and on the ITSERR platform (<https://www.itserr.it/>)

No specific methods or software tools are needed to access the data.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

- Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>)
- HuggingFace.co (<https://huggingface.co/itserr>)
- ITSERR platform (<https://www.itserr.it/>)
- GitHub (<https://github.com/itserr-resilience>)

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

- Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>)
- HuggingFace.co (<https://huggingface.co/itserr>)
- ITSERR platform (<https://www.itserr.it/>)
- GitHub (<https://github.com/itserr-resilience>)

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided? Is there a need for a data access committee?

Only data and documents with a public status will be made accessible via Zenodo. Non-public deliverables and outputs will reside in the project repository on Google Drive. On Zenodo, metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is necessary to retrieve it.

2.3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Are the data produced in the project technically interoperable? Adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins are ways to ensure interoperability.

All data is stored in its original format (e.g. txt, Excel) and storage in open formats (e.g. CSV) is encouraged. Git repositories is used for code management and sharing. In terms of AI, we will produce model files in gguf format.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

ITSERR research data and documentation, when relevant and possible (e.g. no IPR or privacy issues), will be findable and accessible via Zenodo and be assigned standard metadata.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow interdisciplinary interoperability?

When using platforms such as Zenodo, we will always refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g. license ([Open Definition](#)), funders ([FundRef](#)) and grants ([OpenAIRE](#)).

To ensure that our research Work packages use the same vocabularies and to allow an easy data mapping within different European Research contexts, we created two DMP templates:

1. **For Data:** called IOSSG Template for ITSERR and available at <https://argos.openaire.eu>. This template uses interoperable data types and has been published and used by the WP Leaders of ITSERR to implement their WP Data Management Plan.

Figure 1: IOSSG Template for ITSERR as implement on openaire.eu platform

2. **For Software:** called IOSSG Template for ITSERR and will be available at <https://argos.openaire.eu> as soon the Argos team declares it finalised. This template uses almost only interoperable data types from Version 2 of [CodeMeta metadata schema](#). In the picture below is presented the set of data selected to create a "Software Data Management Plan" up to the widgets used to present the data.

Origin	CodeMeta Metadata	Question for Argos	Description and Example	Mandatory	Selected for	Widget type	List of Values (Software Context / Religious Studies)
CodeMetaV2	@type	What is the type of the software?	The type of the software (e.g., "Desktop Software")	Mandatory	Y	Checkbox	Desktop software, Mobile Software, Software as a
CodeMetaV2	@id	What is the unique identifier for the software?	ITSERR/RESILIENCE RI uses Zenodo but there are other DOI	Optional	Y	Free text	-
CodeMetaV2	relatedIdentifier	What are other related identifiers for the software?	List of related identifiers (e.g., "10.5281/zenodo.1003151")	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	codeMeta:referencePublication	What is the reference publication (academic publication related)	Reference publication (e.g., DOI or URL)	Optional	Y	Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	name	What is the name of the software?	The name of the software (e.g., "CodeMeta-Example")	Mandatory	Y	Free text	-
CodeMetaV2	description	Provide a brief description of the software.	A brief description of the software	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	applicationCategory	What is the main category of the software?	The main category (e.g., "Data Analysis")	Mandatory	Y	Select	- Data Analysis
CodeMetaV2	schema:targetProduct	What are the main targets of the software?	Target product (e.g., Data Analysis Tool)	Mandatory	Y	Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	applicationSubCategory	What is the sub-category of the software?	The sub-category (e.g., "Natural Language Processing")	Mandatory	Y	Select	- Natural Language Processing
CodeMetaV2	Person	Who is the person's information?	Responsible information (e.g., "John Doe"). It could be the	Mandatory	Y	Free text	-
CodeMetaV2	author	Who are the authors of the software? Explain and detail if they	Authors information (e.g., "John Doe, Jane Smith")	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	contributor	Who are the contributors to the software? Explain and detail if	Contributors information (e.g., "Alice Johnson, Bob Brown")	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	dateCreated	When was the software created?	The creation date of the software (e.g., "2022-01-01")	Mandatory	Y	Date picker	-
CodeMetaV2	creator	Who is the creator of the software?	Creators information (e.g., "John Doe, Jane Smith")	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	datePublished	When was the software first published?	The date when the software was published. Example: "2023-	Mandatory	Y	Date picker	-
CodeMetaV2	funding	What are the funding sources for the software?	List of funding sources (e.g., "National Science Foundation Grant	Mandatory	Y	Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	version	What is the current version of the software?	The current version of the software (e.g., "1.0.0")	Mandatory	Y	Free text	-
CodeMetaV2	dateModified	What is the date of the last version?	The last modification date of the software (e.g., "2022-04-	Mandatory	Y	Date picker	-
CodeMetaV2	developmentStatus	What is the current development status of the software?	The development status (e.g., "Active", "Deprecated")	Mandatory	Y	Select	Active, Deprecated, Planning, Suspended, Inactive
CodeMetaV2	maintainer	Who is responsible for the maintenance of the software?	Maintainers information (e.g., "John Doe")	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	downloadUrl	What is the URL for downloading the software?	The download URL (e.g., "https://github.com/CodeMeta-Exa	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	schema:softwareHelp	Where can users find help for the software?	Help URL (e.g., https://help.example.com)	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	codeRepository	What is the URL of the software's code repository?	The URL of the code repository (e.g., "https://github.com/Co	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	documentation	What is the URL of the software's documentation?	The documentation URL (e.g., "https://codemeta-	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	encoding	What encoding format is used for the software?	Encoding format used by the software. Example: "UTF-8"	Mandatory	Y	Checkbox	UTF-8, UTF-16, ASCII, ISO-8859-1, Other
CodeMetaV2	hasPart	Does the software have any related parts or components? What	A related part or component of the software. Example:	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	isPartOf	Is the software a part of a larger project or software suite? If	The larger project or software suite that the software is a	Mandatory	Y	Boolean	-
CodeMetaV2	programmingLanguage	What programming language(s) is used to develop the	The list of programming languages used for the	Mandatory	Y	Checkbox	"JavaScript", "Python", "Java", "C#", "C++", "TypeScript", "PH
SMP	dataStandardUsed	Do you use existing and standard input /	yes or No	Mandatory	Y	Boolean	-
CodeMetaV2	preservation	What are the preservation plans for the software?	The preservation plans (e.g., "Long-term storage on Zenodo")	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	citation	What is the recommended citation for the software?	The recommended citation (e.g., "Doe, J., & Smith, J. (2022).	Mandatory	Y	Rich Text area	-
CodeMetaV2	license	What is the software's license?	The software's license (e.g., "https://spdx.org/licenses/MIT")	Mandatory	Y	Select	"MIT License", "GNU General Public License
CodeMetaV2	isAccessibleForFree	Is the software accessible for free?	yes or No	Mandatory	Y	Boolean	-
ITSERR	accessibilityType	What is the type of accessibility?	The accessibility status (e.g., free of charge, free for non-	Mandatory	Y	Select	"Open Source", "Freeware", "Free for Non-Commercial
CodeMetaV2	copyrightHolder	Who holds the copyright of the software?	Copyright holder's name. Example: "John Doe"	Mandatory	Y	Free text	-
CodeMetaV2	copyrightYear	What is the copyright year for the software?	The year the software is copyrighted. Example: "2023"	Mandatory	Y	Date picker	-
ITSERR	partIdenticalLicense	Are parts of the system or some components licensed	Yes or no	Mandatory	Y	Boolean	-
ITSERR	licenseInformation	URL to the document that describes the license information of th	The documentation URL (e.g., "https://codemeta-example.re	Mandatory	Y	Free text	-

Figure 2: Metadata dataset of the Software DMP propose to Argos/OpenAIRE

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Any uncommon or project specific ontologies or vocabularies will be documented appropriately so that mapping can be provided.

2.3.4 MAKING DATA RE-USABLE

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

All data and documents defined with a public status will be shared under the CC-BY license. Sufficient information and metadata will be provided for interpretation of the data. Code will, if possible (e.g. other license types when reusing existing ecosystems or proprietary software may occur), be licensed under OSI approved licenses. The source code will be documented according to established practices. Documentation will be provided in text-based form.

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

At the latest, the data will be made available for re-use upon the 31/10/2025, the end of the ITSERR project. Papers and data will be published starting mid-2023.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

The data that is shared after the project will have no restrictions on re-use.

Documents and data that are not intended for public use will not be accessible or usable by third parties.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data that is shared will have no restrictions on re-use.

Describe data quality assurance processes.

The cloud storage is organized according to working Packages and purpose of the document, to be maintained by the corresponding WP leaders.

The storage offers a detailed history of all changes made in a library

2.4 COSTS AND ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. How will these be covered?

Most of the dissemination of public deliverables will be done via Zenodo which is free of charge.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The Centro Nazionale della Ricerca (CNR) is responsible for data management in collaboration with the WP leaders, who produce and collect relevant data as part of their respective work packages. The WP leaders are tasked with communicating any significant changes to the conditions outlined in the DMP to CNR. CNR is responsible for the DMP and its updates. The WP leaders oversee maintaining file storage related to the activities of their WP. CNR is responsible for informing them about this and reminding them of their responsibilities.

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides on what data will be kept and for how long)?

Zenodo guarantees the preservation of both data files and metadata free of cost.

2.5 DATA STORAGE AND SECURITY

Where will the data be stored?

- In an external cloud service

Data and documents created by the consortium as part of the construction and daily activities of the project are stored and managed using Google Drive storage.

Public deliverables and project outcomes will also be uploaded and made available via Zenodo.

- On the ITSERR platform

The data storage of the ITSERR platform will be ensured by the CNR data centre for at least 10 years through the D4Science services (<https://www.d4science.org/>).

Transmission security for remote access is provided by CNR and ITSERR platform.

Which back-up procedures are in place?

Google Drive maintains backups of primary data for disaster recovery and business continuity purposes — for example, hardware failure, data centre outage, or natural disasters like earthquake, hurricane and so on.

On the ITSERR platform, the CNR has established professional backup and recovery services for at least 175+ research virtual environments.

Where will the data be preserved for the longer term?

Public deliverables will be stored and published on Zenodo.

Zenodo guarantees the preservation of both data files and metadata.

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Zenodo guarantees the preservation of both data files and metadata.

2.6 ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Some data (mainly for WP6 Plorabunt from media documentation on person and places and for WP6 Sanctuaria from surveys) will be created in collaboration with people.

1. Respondents will be fully aware of the nature and purpose of the research and the type of data collected. They will participate on a voluntary basis.
2. When the documentation collected have been already openly published, they could remain opened. Otherwise, sensitive data will not be published.

Only anonymized survey result summaries will be shared and only internally in the consortium.

3 DMP material created for the ITSERR project

Here is a list of material created for the ITSERR project and made available to all colleagues:

From the RESILIENCE RI project:

1. **Data Management Practices Resilience RI** – Michiel De Clerck & Roxanne Wyns (KU Leuven – LIBIS)
2. **Checklist for a Data Management Plan, v4.0**, DCC. (2013). Checklist for a Data Management Plan. v.4.0. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available online: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans>

From the ITSERR project:

1. **Data Management Plan - Feedback & Instructions– 2023/04/11 (PowerPoint)**
2. **Research Data Management in Research Bologna – 2023/03/29(PowerPoint)**

4 DMP webinars and training

During the first year of the project, the Project Management Office Team organized meetings and training. These events were recorded, and the subsequent material was kept private to the ITSERR team members and published internally on YouTube.

1. **Training on Management Processes held on 19/12/2022**: It covered Data Management and Data Management Plan, presentation of RESILIENCE Data Management Best Practices, Documentation Management, Meetings Management, Training Management and Monthly Progress reporting input
2. **Data Management Services - 1st meeting on Data Management strategy - 20/12/2022**: A first conversation at 360° with the University of KU Leuven, University of Modena-Reggio and CNR to define a working strategy and planning encounters for the WP12 Data Management Services
3. **Research Data Management (RDM) Presentation - Meeting held on 29/03/2023**: This meeting was the opportunity to present the Research Data Management Lifecycle. In effect, it was noted during the feedback session about the Data Management Plan that there was a lack of awareness about some aspects of the RDM. This meeting was held to provide a series of pointers towards resources covering those aspects.
4. **Feedback on First DMPs meeting held on 11/04/2023**: This session was organized to collect the feedback of all WPs members that had already created their first DMP. We evaluated the issues uncovered by our colleagues and as PMO we proposed solutions to finalise the step of the creation of the first version of their WP DMP.
5. **Data Management Plan - Transfer to the ITSERR Data DMP "IOSSG ITSERR template" 17/11/2023**: This training was the opportunity to take a DMP already created and transfer the data of the DMP into the template that ITSERR developed with openAIRE and that will be used by the project.

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